

Real-time water monitoring with advanced biosensor systems

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Introduction & Context

The European project BioSensei (Biosensor-based diagnostic platform enabling real-time monitoring of existing and emerging pollutants) is an innovative project focused on the development of a **biosensor-based real-time monitoring system** for typical **nutrients** (nitrates and phosphates), and **Estrogenic endocrine-disruptors, PFAS** (Perfluoroalkyl, and polyfluoroalkyl substances) and **Microcystines**.

BioSensei cope with the EU Drinking Water Directive¹ revision from January 2023 to provide higher human health protection by implementing more stringent water quality standards, tackling pollutants of concern, such as PFAS, endocrine disruptors (EDs) and microcystins.

¹Drinking water directive [Online] <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2020/2184/oj> (accessed: Jun. 27 2024)

Project at a glance

Budget 4,8M€ / 36 months (2024-2027)
Call HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-6
9 partners
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BioSensei approach

- Development of novel transducers and cellular based biosensor for tailored and reliable **biosensors platform** → bimodal sensing approach (electrochemical and fluorescence-based sensors)
- **Real-time** and robust monitoring and **in situ** detection of abiotic and biotic pollutants in **soil moisture** and **watercourses**
- Deployment in **4 use-cases** in Ireland, the Netherlands and Industrial use-cases: PFAS in incoming water required for production; screening for pollutants in a marine protected area for soil and water (fresh, salt); Regulatory control of river water and Domestic environment
- Dissemination and information on existing and future policy

BioSensei vision

- To enhance water quality
- To achieve the highest standards for groundwater in Europe by advancing real-time, cell-based water quality monitoring technologies
- To minimize the harmful impacts of water pollution on ecosystems and human health
- To provide region and application-specific data fostering both climate mitigation in different climatic zones and raising awareness of pollution prevalence

BioSensei consortium at CSEM office in June 2024

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